

Pricing strategies and corporate profitability of manufacturing companies in Rivers State

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Pricing strategies and policies are important marketing decisions that exert significant effect on corporate profitability and industry competitiveness. Despite the role price plays in the purchase decision of customers, the determining role of pricing strategies in corporate profitability has received less traction. This study explored the effect of pricing strategies on corporate performance of manufacturing companies in Rivers State. This investigate seeks to assess how competitive-, cost- and customer value-based pricing strategies influence corporate profitability. The study assessed this relationship by employing cross-sectional research design and utilizing quantitative methods. The data collection process involved the use of structure questionnaire administered to a sample of 318 employees of the selected manufacturing companies in Port Harcourt using the stratified sampling method. The data were coded and imported into the SPSS software and analysed using regression method and descriptive analysis conducted. The regression result showed that competitive-based pricing had positive and significant effect on corporate profitability. Regarding cost-based pricing, it was revealed that the impact on corporate profitability was positive and insignificant. Also, the result shows that customer value-based pricing significantly enhance corporate profitability. These findings indicates that, manufacturing companies that adopt competitive-based and customer value-based pricing strategies are expected to experience higher corporate profit margins. These results have serious policy implications. To enhance better profitability, the study recommends that companies adopt competitive-based and customer value-based pricing. Also, manufacturing companies should maintain the focus of pricing not only on competitors, but also on potential and current customers.

Keywords: Pricing Strategies, Corporate profitability, Competitive-based, and cost-based pricing

INTRODUCTION

In this current dispensation, organizations are grappling with fast changing revolutionary trends; high speed technological advancement, deregulation, accelerated introduction of new products, and demographic changes, among others. These revibrating trends have elevated the business operating landscape, scaling up the degree of competition. The options now open to companies in this fierce competitive business ecosphere is either to become competitive high-performers or exist the market. This has fuelled the need for organizations to become successful and enhance their performance. Traditionally, the success and performance of organizations is

perceived through the financial lens of profit. As emphasized by Friedman (1959), businesses being an abstract entity have one social responsibility and this entails increasing profit and working towards maximizing the wealth of its stockholders. Achieving higher level of performance delivers an array of benefits like an improvement in the financial health of the company, increasing the ability to attract the best minds, to expand operation and explore regional and international market, fostering brand loyalty, improve innovative capacity, attract investors and facilitate the building a robust capital base. The import and impetus of attaining higher

performance level has facilitated organizations to invest increasing amounts of resources the design of internal business strategies capable of upscaling its profitability level.

The manufacturing sector in Rivers State and Nigeria at large has experienced fundamental changes and performance of the sub-sector has fluctuated in the recent decades. Faced with structural problems such as low energy supply, multiple taxation, high interest rate, difficulty in accessing credit facilities from financial institutions, high energy cost, lack of growth supportive infrastructures, foreign exchange access problem, among other have worsen the ease of doing business and undermine the performance of manufacturing firms. The twin reform policies of subsidy removal and floating of the naira in the third quarter of 2023 has exacerbated the operation cost and exchange rate risk faced by manufacturing firms, with many manufacturing firms finding it difficult to pass on some of the costs to end users through higher prices without undermining their performance. The growth of the manufacturing sector has been weak and fluctuated in the recent decades. In Q2 2016, the manufacturing sector grew by -3.36% and improved slight to growing at 0.81% in Q1 2019. The activities in the sector dipped further to -0.13 in Q2 2019 and rebounded, growing at 8.78% in Q2 2020. Growth in the sector fell from 8.78% recorded in Q2 2020 1.51% in Q4 2020. The sector recorded recovery growing by 3.40% in Q1 2021; 3.49% in Q2 2021 and 4.29% in Q3 2021, before falling to 1.91% in Q3 2022 (NBS, 2022). From 2023, the manufacturing sector has experienced fluctuating level of performance, growing by 1.61% in Q1 2023; 2.2% in Q2 2023; 0.48% in Q3 2023 and 1.38% in Q4 2023 (NBS, 2023). In Q1 2024, activities in the manufacturing sector picked up growing at 1.49% and declined to 1.28% in Q2 2024 (NBS, 2024). The importance of increased performance of the manufacturing firm can be appraised at the micro- and macro-level. At the micro-level, higher performance of the manufacturing firms ensures improved supply of goods and services, which ensures reduction in price of commodity items. The success of manufacturing firms increases labour demand, creating more jobs. At the macro level, performance of manufacturing firms contributes to the growth of the Nigerian economy and export of the firms improves the external reserve position and stabilizes the exchange rate of the naira. In addition, Nigerian is likely to operate a balance of trade surplus and favourable balances of payments as performance of manufacturing companies improve.

A number of factors have been suggested as factors that determine the performance of manufacturing firms, one of such factors is pricing strategy. Nagle, Hogan & Zale (2016) emphasized the pivotal role of pricing strategy by positing that, competitive pricing can improve performance by enhancing customer loyalty and brand perception. Pricing strategy also influences consumer

purchasing behaviour and plays crucial role in their purchasing decision process. This importance of adopting an effective pricing strategy as a fundamental determinant of performance has been emphasized by empirical studies (see Manuere, Gwangwava & Jengeta, 2015; Nafuna, Masaba, Tumwine, Watundu, Bonareri & Nakola, 2019; Wawaka & Muchelule, 2018; Arif & Subrahmanyam, 2022; Ojodu, Ajibayo & Bulugbe, 2023). Thus, strategic pricing defined by the internal capacity of the company is required in order to enhance the profitability of companies. In lieu of this, this study elects to examine the implication of pricing strategies on the profitability of manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2, following the section, dwells on the theoretical background and review of empirical literature. The methodology adopted was presented in Section 3. Section 4 present the results and Section 5 concludes the study and offer policy recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Operational Conceptual Framework of the relationship between Pricing strategies and Organization Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Rivers State.

Source: Author (2024)

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The linkage between pricing strategy and organization performance has been situated within certain theoretical framework, among which are the neoclassical price theory and the resource-based view (RBV) theory. The

neoclassical theory follows the work of Marshall (1890) who develop the theory of how price impacts on consumer behaviour. The theory establishes that consumers have varying preferences and tastes, rational and choose among alternate products that maximize their utility or satisfaction.

The theory emphasise that, utility is what drives the consumption of a product and the willingness of the consumer to part away his/her money balance. The assertion of the theory is that, since price serves the purpose of providing information on the amount a consumer is willing to give up in exchange for a product, the price placed on the product supplied by the organization will depend on the fundamental of the relationship between the marginal utility from consuming an additional unit of the product and the price of the additional unit (Uwaoma, Ahamefula & Nwangu, 2024). Moreso, the assumption that the marginal utility derived from consuming additional unit of a product diminishes as more of the item is consumed suggests that buyers rationally rank their consumption activities in increasing preferences, and in consideration to price purchase the high-ranking product. This theory conclusively points out that price is at the heart of the purchasing decision of consumers and the performance of an organization is intractably linked to the pricing strategies adopted. The resource-based view theory pioneered by Peter & Barney (1957) describes and forecast how business entities can gain long-run competitive advantage and upscale their performance level to higher echelon through the acquisition and management of its finite resources (Nagode, Adeyemi & Abogunrin, 2022).

The theory emphasize that the resources of the firm are predictors of its performance and competitive advantage. The RBV conceptualize firms as bundles of capabilities and resources, with which firms compete and these resources and/or capabilities are not tradeable on the open markets, thus making them inimitable, rare, and non-substitutable.

According to Nagode, et al., (2022), these resources are categorized into three, namely, human, organizational and physical assets. The theory emphasizes the adoption of an inside-out business strategy, wherein the internal unique capabilities and resources of the firm are used to outperform it competitors. The theory posits that certain strategies practices could enhance or dampen the performance level of the firm. Within the context of the study, the RBV is an appropriate theory that provides connecting relationship between pricing strategy and firm performance, as pricing strategies in the dimension of competition-based, cost-based, among others, can be considered internal strategies that can be weaponized by organizations to affect their performance. The pricing strategies can be perceived as a reflection of managerial skills which can be developed to provide competitive edge for the firm in contrast to its industry peers and improve its performance.

Review of Empirical Literature

Mwito, Rintari & Muema (2024) studied twenty-five small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Imenti North Sub-county, located in Kenya, as the explored the implication of pricing strategies on the growth of SMEs. They hypothesized that the value-based pricing approaches do not engender growth of SMEs in the county. In exploring and empirically testing this hypothesis, the simple random method was relied upon in selecting 8 SMEs from the population of 25 SMEs. The opinion sought after were provided by specific employees of the SMEs which were marketing, finance and procurement managers, and marketing, finance and procurement officers, totaling one hundred and two. The test for reliability of the questionnaire used to collect the requisite data was performed using the Cronbach method and the coefficient exceeded 0.7, indicating reliability of the instrument. This was followed by empirical analysis of the data using mean and correlation methods. The provided empirical results suggesting that the adoption of value-based pricing strategy enhanced the growth of the SMEs studied, as the correlation estimate was positive and significant.

Gikera & Bula (2023) in their empirical research tried to determine the implication of adopting product pricing as a pricing strategy and gauge the likely effect of it on performance. Their survey of the relationship focused on maize seed companies, as they targeted twenty-four such corn seed companies that operate in the county of Nairobi, Kenya. Combining the simple random and stratified sampling procedures, the authors selected 5 employees each from the 24 maize companies, culminating to 120 respondents. To obtain relevant data, standardized questionnaires were administered to the sampled respondents using the drop and pick later method. The analysis of the data was performed using mean, standard deviation, correlation and regression methods. Basically, the authors tried to determine the effective pricing strategy among promotions, packaging and segmentation that enhances organization performance, for which profitability, market share and sales volumes were used as approximate measures. They show that product pricing is strong strategies that effectively determine performance. The regression outcome supported the correlation results as an increase in product pricing significantly improves the probability of the maize companies performing better.

Nkem & Onuoha (2023) like previous contributions probe the connecting linkage between pricing strategy and performance, however, their survey focused on fast food restaurants that run their services in Port Harcourt. To achieve the objective of their study, the combined the quasi-experimental and cross-sectional survey approaches and targeted one hundred and fifty (150) registered fast food restaurants that has been delivering such service for at least ten (10) years. With the

purposive sampling procedure, the research narrowed down the restaurants, as they engaged only ten (10) restaurants. The authors gathered information from the one hundred and five (105) respondents using structured questionnaire, which exhibited instrument validity and reliability as confirmed through relevant tests. The retrieved data was put through analysis with the help of the correlation method. They show based on the Spearman results that all three measures of pricing strategy (customer value-based, cost-based and competition-based) significantly promote restaurant performance.

Agboola & Ayo (2024) in their survey gathered primary information through the use of questionnaire and assessed the implication of adopting innovative pricing strategy on profitability. Their descriptive survey concentrated on agricultural SMEs that undertake their entrepreneurial activities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Their study which followed a cross-sectional approach targeted two hundred and fifty-three (253) registered agricultural SMEs. They restricted the SMEs to only producers and processors in three subsectors, namely, crop, livestock and fisheries. Through random sampling, about one hundred and fifty-three (153) respondents were selected and information relating to the subject matter were extracted to the selected respondents through issued questionnaire. The developed questionnaire was verified to be reliable and valid and a regression model was setup to examine the relationship among variables of interest. The result show that innovative pricing strategy significantly predicts profitability, as the estimation outcome revealed the effect of innovative pricing to be positive.

Yakubu, Shehu & Ben (2019) for a population of over 1000 employees of hi-malt and 7up bottling company operating in Kaduna, assessed the pricing strategies adopted by the understudy companies and its implication on customer's loyalty. They randomly selected 100 employees with 100% response rate. In examining whether pricing strategies matters for customer loyalty, questionnaire patterned in a 5-point scale developed by Likert was used to solicit responses from selected employees. They used the Chi-square method in investigating this relationship and the results from the estimation performed revealed that pricing strategy and price satisfaction enhances customer loyalty.

Osho & Shaka (2022) explored the linkage between transactions transfer pricing policies and corporate performance, zeroing on organizations in Nigeria. For their empirical study, the empirical investigation was reduced to a cross-section of food and beverage companies whose equity are bought and sold on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). A population of twenty-one firms was targeted and through random sampling only five were selected for the inquisition. The sample of five firms used for the investigation was Berger, Coca-Cola, Unilever, Nestle and Presco. The relationship was

investigated for the period covering from 2012 to 2021 and they controlled for other factors with determining influence on performance [with profit after tax (PAT) as measure] such as interest rate, exchange rate and inflation rate. They suggested that transfer pricing scale up PAT, but the increase in PAT as the pricing strategy is employed is insignificant. They did show that PAT increases when there is an increase in interest rate. Both inflation and exchange rate undermine performance, though the decline in PAT when both rates increase is insignificant.

De Toni, Milan, Saciloto & Larentis (2017) performed an empirical study on 150 metal-mechanic companies that operates in Northeast Rio Grande do Sul State in Brazil. Their empirical survey seeks to examine the pricing strategy that significantly contribute to corporate profitability. They examined the pricing strategy between competition-based, value-based and cost-based that foster better performance for the understudy companies. The collection of the requisite data occurred by administering questionnaire which was sent electronically. The data were gathered between June and August of 2017. The data analysis process of the survey involved the use of correlation and the hierarchical regression (OLS). It was identified from the correlation analysis that higher prices generate strong business performance and companies that adopt customer value-based prices display higher profit margins. In contrast, they observed from the regression estimation that companies who adopt customer value-based pricing strategy and set high prices for their commodities yield higher profit margin relative to competitors that favour competition-based pricing model and price their goods lower.

Ojodu, Ajibayo & Bulugbe (2023) explored through cross-sectional survey explored whether value-based and/or cost-based pricing strategy carries performance effect. Basically, they tried to analyse if the use of the aforementioned pricing strategies induces higher performance. In order to assess this relationship, they used the convenient sampling procedure wherein one hundred and ninety-five (195) employees were sampled. The data collection process followed the administration of questionnaire, which was validated and certified reliable, to the 195 respondents and upon cleaning of the responses, only 175 were useable. The information extracted through issued questionnaire were analyse by regression, using the OLS method. With regards to the predictive strength of the pricing strategies, they identified that organization performance is higher when companies adopt cost-based and value-based pricing system or strategy, and the use of these pricing strategies significantly guarantees upscaled performance level.

Osano & Lutego (2022) predicated their work on the reasoned action theory as they tried to understand, through descriptive survey, whether the pricing strategies adopted by organizations has implication for repeated

purchases by customer and ultimately customer retention. Their investigation covered metal fabricators and mechanics that operate at the satellite industrial sites in Mwanza city, Tanzania. From the aggregate of 570 small scale metal work operators, they purposively sampled 228 operators and this constituted the respondents to which questionnaires were administered. The regression (OLS) method was used to analyse retrieved data and identify among the pricing constructs of value-based, cost-based and competition-based pricing the most potent in upscaling performance. The estimation produced impressive discoveries with policy implications. The authors illustrated that small scale metal work operators can achieve higher performance heights following usage of cost-based, value-based and competition-based pricing techniques or practices. Overall, the researcher provided empirical backing to pricing strategy being a determining factor on how organization perform.

Azad & Singh (2019) in their descriptive survey assess whether pricing strategy is an important factor that guarantees customer retention. In understanding this relationship, they followed a scientific path, first targeting businesses in Kurdistan. Through the instrumentation of random sampling, 100 business owners were sampled and analysis input data were collected through administered questionnaire. Only 87 questionnaires were deemed usable after sorting and screening of administered copies of questionnaire. In their study, correlation and regression methods were used within the analysis. The findings produced from the correlation analysis demonstrate that the adoption of pricing strategy ensures businesses retain customers. The regression result agrees with the correlation outcome, identifying pricing strategy as positively related to customer retention.

Al-Salamin & Al-Hassan (2016) used questionnaire to collect data which was used to analyse the implication of adopting competitive pricing techniques on customer patronage. The survey was conducted in Al-Hassa in Saudi Arabia and about three hundred and eighty-five (385) respondents from an approximate population of 1,220,655 were sampled as activities who offer opinions based on a set of questions presented to them. The conclusion reached from Chi-square results was that firms who adopt bundle, penetration and discount pricing technique are expected to experience higher customer patronage than those who do not adopt such pricing strategies.

Arif & Subrahmanyam (2022) recognizing the role of price in the operation of the market, used survey data to evaluate if the pricing strategy of firms has consequence on customer retention. Their study specifically explored the penetration pricing practice and gauge its influence in ensuring organizations retain their customers through empirical analysis. The organization studied were international hotels that are based in Kurdistan, Iraq and

seven (7) of such hotels located in Sulaymaniyah, Erbil and Duhok cities were targeted. The sample size was calculated on the basis of rooms and four hundred and fifty-nine (459) respondents were randomly sampled from 1,200 rooms. The linkage between the two variables researched was estimated combining the Chi-square and regression methods. Through the Chi-square analysis, they aver that the adoption of penetration pricing drives customer retentions as it ensures the hotels retain guests.

Vivian (2017) studying large retail supermarkets in Kenya, used data that were collected by administering questionnaire to better understand if adopting pricing strategy, particular the variant of pricing differentiation, will enhance and deliver customer satisfaction. The researcher focused on thirty-one (31) supermarkets from eight (8) regional headquarters, targeting branch managers and customers. Through a multi stage sampling procedure, two hundred and twenty-four (224) respondents were selected for the empirical survey and responses solicited from them using questionnaire. The estimation strategy entailed the use of correlation and regression methods in analysing the data gathered. Both estimation results were definitive as pricing differentiation was identified as a pricing practices corporations seeking to enhance customer satisfaction can adopt, as pricing penetration was positively signed and significant.

Wawaka & Muchelule (2018) conducted a survey of 5 cement manufacturing firms in Kenya as they try to assess the pricing strategies that effectively confers competitive advantage on the understudy firms. Two pricing strategies, namely value-based and competition-based, were explored and the effect of each strategy on competitive advantage assessed empirically. In their study, they targeted 553 employees and departmental heads numbering five. 226 employees were selected for indepth analysis and this was achieved through the use of stratified random sampling. The data collected using questionnaire were analyse for causal linkage among the variables studied using regression and correlation analysis. The results show positive coefficients for the two pricing strategies, indicating that companies that use competition-based and value-based pricing strategy fosters competitive and gives companies competitive edge in contrast to their competitors.

Nafuna, Masaba, Tumwine, Watundu, Bonareri & Nakola (2019) carried out a cross-sectional analysis and used data of employees of private primary schools to explore whether the pricing strategy used by companies determine their ability to consistently perform better or become more profitable and highly liquid. A total of 123 schools in Kampala district in Uganda were randomly sampled in the exploration of this empirical linkage and data were collected from bursar, headteachers and resident directors through the use of questionnaire. They measured the pricing strategy in terms of perceived value, cost based and competitive based. In addition,

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis Results

Details	Classifications	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	199	62.6
	Female	119	37.4
	Total	318	100.0
Age	18-29 years	98	30.8
	30-39 years	104	32.7
	40-49 years	67	21.1
	50 years and above	49	15.4
	Total	318	100.0
Marital Status	Single	118	37.1
	Married	149	46.9
	Divorced	19	6.0
	Separated	32	10.1
	Total	318	100.0
Education	OND/HND	97	30.5
	Bachelors	151	47.5
	Masters	57	17.9
	PhD	13	4.1
	Total	318	100.0
Work Experience	Less than 1 year	9	2.8
	1-5 years	125	39.3
	6-10 years	96	30.2
	11-15 years	75	23.6
	16 years and above	13	4.1
	Total	318	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

they branched their investigation in ascertaining whether competitive advantage is a mediator in how pricing strategy is linked with performance. The analysis of this and previous objectives was done through the use of regression (OLS) method. They demonstrated through the OLS method that the usage of cost-based and perceived value-based pricing yields higher performance level. Also, they showed that a much higher performance level is attained through the use of these pricing strategies when the firm gains higher competitive advantage.

Manuere, Gwangwava & Jengeta (2015) on SMEs in Zimbabwe probed the link with pricing strategy and firm success, with the intention of assessing if the pricing strategy used by the SMEs dictates their level of success. From the three hundred and fifty (350) SMEs in Gokwe district, they randomly selected fifty (50) SMEs owners and solicited responses from them through administered questionnaire. These researchers disclosed that profit strategic pricing is an effective pricing strategy that can promote firm success as evidence of the pricing strategy positively correlated with firm success was found upon empirical analysis.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

Data and research design

The objective of this research is to assess whether

pricing strategies has significant influence on the performance of selected manufacturing firms. To this end, the study uses data of manufacturing companies in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. A cross-sectional design was used in investigating this problem.

Sampling Technique and Sample

Employees of the manufacturing companies that operate in Port Harcourt were surveyed. These manufacturing firms and employees were selected on the basis of stratified sampling as these firms comprise of 2,579 employees. A common issue encountered when working with target population is the difficulty in obtaining and processing information. As a result, a sample of the employees that represent the population was used and arrived at using the Yamane's (1967) formula.

Data collection instrument

The questionnaire framed in the dimension of the 5-points scale as developed by Likert were administered to employees of the manufacturing companies selected for this investigation. The involvement of the employees of the selected companies in the survey is explain in part by the fact that though pricing strategy decisions are made by top and mid-level employees, the implementation of the decision is carried out across board. The use of questionnaire in collecting data was preferred over

Table 2: Regression Results showing Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adj. R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.723 ^a	0.523	0.497	0.4991	1.873

a. Predictors: (Constant), Competitive-based, cost-based, customer value-based

b. Dependent variable: Corporate Profitability

interviews as it ensures respondent anonymity, the flexibility for respondent boost response rate, enhances data accuracy and reduces reporting biases. The questionnaire was used to collect data on the employees' characteristics such as gender, age, education, marital status and years of working with the organization. These characteristics make up section A of the research instrument and the second part which is section B collects data on opinions relating to the constructs of pricing strategies and the measure of organization performance.

Data Analysis procedure

To evaluate the construct of pricing strategies that have predicting effect on organization performance, the data collected through questionnaire were screened, coded and imported into the SPSS software for analysis. Both descriptive and inferential analysis was performed on the collected data. The descriptive statistics computed was percentage and frequencies. The inferential statistics carried out was the multiple regression model. This model permits the analysis of the pricing strategies constructs that influence organization performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive analysis of the characteristics of the surveyed participants is captured in Table 1. A total of three hundred and forty-six (346) copies of questionnaire was administered and returned. The returned copies of questionnaire were then screen for omission and incompleteness and after successful screening, it was discovered that three hundred and eighteen (318) are usage and this represent a response rate of 91%. Subsequent analysis, inclusive of descriptive analysis, was conducted on the basis of the usage questionnaire. This section describes the items on the first section of the questionnaire. Here the distribution of the participants that are females and males are calculated and from the output, 62.6% are male and 37.4% are females, giving about 199 males and 119 females. The study categorized the age of those surveyed into four groups of 18 – 29; 30 – 39; 40 – 49, and 50 years and above. The descriptive results put the proportion of the randomly selected employees that fall within this age categories as 30.8% for those between 18 – 29 years; 32.7% for 30 – 39 years; 21.1% for those aged 40 – 49 years and the

proportion of those surveyed in the last age category is 15.4%. The marital status of those surveyed were described and summarized in Table 1. For those single, analysed result shows an estimate of about 37.1% or 118 respondents and 149 employees or 46.9% of the 318 sampled are married. Regarding the respondents that are either divorced or separated, the former makes up 6% of the surveyed and 10.1% constitute the latter. To understand the educational level of the employees across all three organizational level, the study considered those with first degrees (OND/HND and Bachelor), second degrees (masters) and third degrees (PhD). From collected data, the proportion of those surveyed with OND/HND degree is 30.5%, those with bachelor degrees make up 47.5%, while those with masters and doctorate degrees are 57 and 13 respectively. Lastly, employees with 1 – 5 years experiences are 125, followed by those with 6 – 10 years and represent 30.2% of the total sample. 13 respondents indicated having at least 16 years' experience and 2.8% of surveyed participants indicated having being on the job for less than a year. Summarily, those sampled for this survey are youth, agile, educated and display high years of experience.

Inferential Analysis

For testing the sets of hypotheses that guide this study, the collected data after been coded and imported into the SPSS software were analysed by regression method, which enable the study to estimate the coefficients of the pricing strategies constructs separately on the profitability level of the companies studied. These results are presented in Table 2 – 4.

Table 2 shows the predictive power of the model estimated. The estimated R value of 0.723 show partial positive correlation between the pricing strategy constructs. As revealed by Table 2, an R square value of 0.523 was calculated, revealing the predictive power of the estimated model. The calculated value of 0.523 reveals that 52.3% of changes in the profitability level of the companies studied is directly caused by competitive-based, cost-based and customer value-based pricing strategies of the companies. This means that competitive-based, cost-based and customer value-based pricing strategies dictate about 52.3% of the fluctuation in the profit level, alluding to pricing strategy strongly influencing the bottom line of the manufacturing companies.

A strong assumption for using regression analysis in

Table 3: Analysis of Variance

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.011	3	5.004	20.086	0.000 ^b
	Residual	13.701	254	0.249		
	Total	28.712	318			

a. Dependent variable: Corporate Profitability

b. Predictors: (Constant), Competitive-based, cost-based, customer value-based

Table 4: Coefficients of Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>		
Constant	0.644	0.433		1.489	0.142
Competitive-based	0.436	0.093	0.487	4.707	0.000
Cost-based	0.188	0.099	0.189	1.899	0.063
Customer value-based	0.196	0.073	0.270	2.693	0.009

Source: Author's computation (2024)

estimating relationship between certain variables is that a linear relationship exists between the selected variables. The estimated coefficients are expected to be consistent and efficient when linearity of estimates is confirmed. Thus, the study for hypothesis of linearly unrelated variables against the hypothesis that the selected variables are linear in estimates. This test is based on the F-ratio and the experimentation of the hypothesis follows the probability approach. Table 3 shows that the F-ratio statistics of 20.086 is highly significant at 1%. Hence, the hypothesis that speaks to the variables not linearly related is rejected and it is consequent that pricing strategy constructs and the indicator of profitability can be linearly combined and the estimates for each constructs calculated.

The pricing strategy that influences profitability are calculated using regression method. Table 4 presents the result showing the pricing strategy among cost-based, competitive-based and customer value-based pricing strategies that impact the profitability of the understudy firms. Based on the regression analysis presented in Table 4, the study can evaluate the pricing strategy that has predictive power on profitability and test the hypotheses. The regression result indicates that the estimated average coefficient for competitive-based pricing is 0.436, revealing that the profitability level of the companies increases when the competitive-based strategy is used. The usage of the competitive-based strategy is expected to increase profitability by approximately 0.436%. The increase in profitability level when the competitive-based strategy is adopted is highly significant at 1% level. Thus, the hypothesis that competitive-based pricing does not significantly affect profitability was not confirmed. This result is consistent with the findings of Gikera & Bula (2023), Nkem & Onuoha (2023) and Agboola & Ayo (2024). Table 3 identify that cost-based strategy improve the profit margin

of the understudy companies, as the study calculated a positive value of 0.188 for cost-based strategy. The second hypothesis (H) that indicates that cost-based strategy did not influence profitability significantly was not rejected as the p-value of the estimate value of 0.188 is below 0.05.

Table 3 shows that under the customer value-based strategy, the profitability level of the companies is expected to improve to a higher level. As illustrated in Table 3, the adoption of this strategy will yield an average of 0.196% increase in profit margin. This means, the use of customer value-based by companies to scale up their profit margin is expected to be effective. This finding corroborates the results of Osho & Shaka (2022), De Toni, Milan, Saciloto & Larentis (2017) and Ojodu, Ajibayo & Bulugbe (2023).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study presents yielding empirical results on the whether pricing strategies has consequence on the corporate profitability of companies. The study assessed this relationship by focusing on manufacturing companies in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study explored the effect of pricing strategies such as competitive-based, cost-based and customer value-based pricing on corporate profitability. This relationship was analysed using regression analysis. The study found evidence suggesting that competitive-based pricing significantly enhance corporate profitability. It was revealed through regression analysis that, the usage of customer value-based pricing strategy yields higher corporate profit margins. The study found evidence that indicates that cost-based pricing insignificantly enhances corporate profitability. Given the necessity of achieving higher corporate profit margins, this study recommends that that

companies adopt competitive-based and customer value-based pricing. Also, manufacturing companies should maintain the focus of pricing not only on competitors, but also on potential and current customers.

REFERENCES

- Agboola, A. O., & Ayo, M. F. (2024). Effect of innovative pricing strategy on agricultural small and medium scale enterprises profitability in Nigeria. *Int. J. Manage. Sci. and Bus. Analysis Res.* 4(7):117-128.
- Al-Salamin, H., & Al-Hassan, E. (2016). The impact of competitive pricing on customer patronage in Saudi Arabia: Al-Hassa case study. *European J. Bus. Manage.* 8(12), 62-79.
- Arif, S. A. F., & Subrahmanyam, S. (2022). Penetration Pricing Strategy and Customer Retention—An Analysis. *J. Positive School Psychol.* 7058-7072.
- Azad, S., & Singh, U. S. (2019). A study on the effect of pricing strategy on customer retention in Kurdistan. *Int. J. Supply Chain Manage.* 8(1), 98-112.
- De Toni, D., Milan, G. S., Saciloto, E. B., & Larentis, F. (2017). Pricing strategies and levels and their impact on corporate profitability. *Revista de Administração (São Paulo)*, 52(2), 120-133.
- Gikera, J. M., & Bula, H. (2023). Effect of product pricing strategy on performance of maize seed companies in Nairobi city county, Kenya. *Int. J. Soc. Sci. Manage. and Entrepreneurship (IJSSME)*, 7(1).
- Manuere, F., Gwangwava, E., & Jengeta, M. (2015). Strategic pricing and firm success: A study of SMEs in Zimbabwe. *Asian J. Bus. Manage.* 3(3).
- Mwito, R. M., Rintari, N., & Muema, W. (2024). Influence of Value-Based Pricing on Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Imenti North Sub-County, Kenya. *Journal of Marketing and Communication*, 4(3), 1-9.
- Nafuna, E., Ayub Kutosi Masaba, D., Tumwine, S., Watundu, S., Bonareri, T. C., & Nakola, N. (2019). Pricing strategies and financial performance: the mediating effect of competitive advantage. Empirical evidence from Uganda, a study of private primary schools. *Global J. Manage. Bus. Res.* 19(1-C), 28-37.
- Nkem, E. P., & Onuoha, B. C. (2023). Pricing strategy and organizational performance of fast-food restaurants in Port Harcourt. *Int. J. Manage. Sci.* 11(10), 22-37.
- Ojodu, H. O., Ajibayo, A. V., & Bulugbe, O. T. (2023). The influence of value-based pricing and cost-based pricing strategy on organisational performance in Nigeria. *Lagos J. Psychol.* 1(1), 165-181.
- Osano, F. J., & Lutego, D. (2022). Effect of pricing strategies on customer retention among small scale metal mechanics and fabrication: A case study of Mwanza City-Tanzania. *Int. J. Engine. Bus. and Manage.* 6(1), 18-28.
- Osho, A., & Shaka, A. (2022). Transactions transfer pricing policies and performance of corporate organizations in Nigeria. *The J. Accounting and Manage.* 12(3).
- Vivian, C. (2017). Pricing differentiation strategy on customer satisfaction in large retail supermarkets in Kenya. *Mara Res. J. Bus. & Manage.* -ISSN, 2519-1381.
- Wawaka, G. E., & Muchelule, Y. (2018). Effect of Pricing Strategies on Competitive Advantage of Selected Cement Manufacturing Firms in Kenya. *J. Bus. Manage.* 5(2), 1254, 1266.
- Yakubu, A. N., Shehu, S., & Ben, N. (2019). The impact of pricing strategy on customer loyalty in a production companies (a case study of hi-malt and 7up bottling company, Kaduna). *J. Manage. and Corporate Gov.* 11(1), 43-56.